

Data Leak Prevention System: A Survey

Prasad Jadhav¹, P. M. Chawan²

¹M. Tech Student, Department of Computer Engineering and IT, VJTI College, Maharashtra, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Computer Engineering and IT, VJTI College, Maharashtra, India

Abstract - In recent years, many companies and institutions tend to keep most of their data in digital format. There is a large specter of information stored by such entities, like medical records, contracts, internal procedures, etc. that can be considered as being confidential, thus protecting them is a great concern. Since employees have access to such information, either by negligence or bad intention, they could leak the information. Hence, information security has become a big concern for the organizations.

In this article we propose a software architecture known as Data Leak Prevention System that can achieve the goals of information security of the organizations. This architecture is designed to highly regulate access to private data, and furthermore, to identify which parts of the system can be subjected to external hacking or inside attacks.

The proposed architecture focuses mainly on preventing massive data leaks. The architecture guarantees that any access to sensitive data is logged into an external system which cannot be affected by the attackers.

Key Words: Data Leak Prevention

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, security has become an essential factor in our day to day life. Security is required in Industrial sector as well as government sector. A malicious attacker can use various methods to access the private information. To avoid this is one of the goals of the information security. As we know that we require security in our daily life, similarly we need to implement various strategies to secure the information.

Data leak is the unauthorized exchange of data between an organization and an external destination or recipient. A data breach or data leak is the release of confidential or sensitive information to the unauthorized users. Data leak can happen because of a programmer assault, intentional leak by employees of the organization, or unintentional loss or exposure of data. It implies that the data is transferred electronically or physically. Data leak usually occurs via the web and email. It can also occur via mobile data storage devices such as optical media, USB keys, and laptops.

Data leak is also known as data theft and is a huge problem for data security. Regardless of size or industry, it can cause serious damage to any organization. Any organization will want to protect themselves from threats like declining revenue, tarnished reputation, massive financial penalties or

lawsuits. There are many different types of data leak like Accidental Breach, Disgruntled or Ill-Intentioned Employee, Electronic Communications with Malicious Intent, etc. and it is important to understand that the problem can be initiated via an internal or external source. The following are common causes of data loss.

- 1. Natural Disaster:** Your hard drive can be damaged due to fire, flood or some other unforeseen disasters. However, the data can still be retrieved in such situations.
- 2. Accidental Damage:** If a drive or disk is mishandled or accidentally dropped, this may cause trauma and loss of data. Data recovery is also possible in this case.
- 3. Accidental drive format:** Sometimes users accidentally format their drives and this results in instant loss of data. However, it is possible to recover your data in a situation like this. Users can get help from the experts.
- 4. Accidental Deletion of Data:** There are times when you accidentally delete a file or a program from your hard drive. This is an unintentional deletion which may go unnoticed for a long time. Administrative errors also fall under this category. The best way is to think carefully before you delete any data or program.
- 5. Intentional Deletion of Data:** You may have deleted a file intentionally from your system and later decided you wanted the file back. You can still recover your data from the recycle bin. If you have emptied your recycle bin, you can use software recover deleted recycle bin files.
- 6. Corrupted Data:** If your file system or database is corrupted, then it will inevitably lead to loss data. At the same time, it is possible to recover data from a corrupt file system using an appropriate software tool.
- 7. Power Failure:** If you experience power failure before you have the opportunity to save your work, you may lose valuable data. It is better to keep saving as your work.
- 8. Software Failure:** When the application software suddenly crashes or freezes while working, this may result in severe damage to the hard drive. This causes the program close suddenly and all unsaved work is lost.

9. Virus Attack: If a machine is deeply infected by viruses and worms, spyware, adware and some deadly computer parasites, this can lead to total corruption and loss of data. Installing a very good anti-virus program will reduce the possibility of having a fatal virus attack.

10. Malicious Attack: Professional hackers or competitors can invade into the system and destroy it. This will obviously lead to loss of data.

Data Leak Prevention (DLP) is the practice of detecting and preventing data breaches, exfiltration, or unwanted destruction of sensitive data. Organizations use DLP to protect their data and comply with regulations and policies. The term DLP refers to defending organizations against both data loss and data leak prevention. The term data leak refers to an event in which important information to the organization is leaked to the unauthorized environment. Data leak prevention focuses on preventing illicit transfer of data outside the institutional boundaries.

Figure 1. DLP: Data Leak Prevention Model

Data Leak Prevention (DLP) systems are increasingly being implemented by various organizations. Unlike the standard security mechanisms such as firewalls and intrusion detection systems (IDS), the DLP systems are designated systems which are used to protect in use, in transit and at rest data. DLP system analytically uses the content and surrounding context of confidential data to detect and prevent unauthorized access to confidential data. DLP system that use content analysis techniques are largely dependent upon regular expressions, data fingerprinting, and statistical analysis to detect data leaks.

2. LITRATURE REVIEW

The following are various methods to implement Data Leak Prevention System:

1. Implementation of a single centralized DLP program:

Many enterprises and business units implement inconsistent and ad hoc DLP systems. This inconsistency results in lack of visibility into data assets and weak data

security. Also, the employees tend to ignore department DLP programs that the rest of the organization does not support.

2. Evaluation of Internal Resources:

To create and implement a DLP system, an organization needs skilled personnel with DLP technical expertise, including DLP risk analysis, data leak response and reporting, data protection laws, and DLP training and awareness. Some government regulations and policies make it mandatory for the organizations to either employ internal staff or retain external consultants with data protection knowledge.

3. Conducting an Inventory and Assessment:

An evaluation of the types of data and their value to the organization serve as prerequisites in implementation of a DLP program. This involves identification of relevant data, determining the location of data, and whether it is intellectual property, confidential information, or data that regulations address. DLP products like McAfee DLP are capable of identifying the information assets by scanning the metadata of files and cataloging the result, or by opening the files to analyze the content. The next step is the evaluation of risk associated with each type of data. In addition to this, data exit points and the cost to the organization in case of data loss are also considered.

4. Implementation in Phases:

Implementation of DLP is a long-term process. The best way is to implement DLP in stages. The most effective approach is to prioritize the types of data and communication channels. Likewise, implementation of DLP software components or modules as needed, based on the organization's priorities should be considered rather than implementing it all at once.

5. Creating a Classification System:

Before an organization can create and implement DLP policies, it needs a data classification framework or taxonomy for both unstructured and structured data. Data security can be classified as confidential, internal, public, personally identifiable information (PII), financial data, regulated data, intellectual property, and others. DLP products can scan data using various methods, which helps the organization to identify the key categories of data. The DLP software automates classification and users can select and customize the categories. Content owners can also visually evaluate certain types of content that cannot be identified using simple keywords or phrases.

6. Establishment of Data Handling and Remediation Policies:

After creating the classification framework for data, the next step is to create policies for handling various types of data. The DLP policies for handling sensitive data are specified by the Government requirements. DLP solutions typically apply policies based on various regulations like HIPAA or GDPR. The policies as per the needs of the organization are customized by the DLP staff. The DLP enforcement products monitor outgoing channels (like email and web chat) and provide options for handling potential security breaches in order to administer the policies. For

example, if an employee is about to send an email with a sensitive attachment, he might receive a pop-up that suggests encrypting the message. The system can block it completely or redirect it to the line manager. The response is based on rules and policies established by the organization.

7. Education and Training of Employees:

Employee awareness and acceptance of security policies is essential for DLP system. Online training, classes, periodic emails, and posters can improve employee understanding of the importance of data security and enhance their ability to follow recommended best DLP approach

3. DLP ARCHITECTURE

Figure 2. Data Leak Prevention System Architecture

The data in an organization is classified into three security classes as top secret, restricted and unrestricted. Whenever the user wants to send data over the internet, this information will be monitored by the DLP system. The system will calculate the semantic similarity and check whether the data is top secret, restricted or unrestricted. If the data is unrestricted, the user can send the information. If it is restricted or top secret, the user will not be allowed to send this information as it may lead to intentional or unintentional data leak.

The organizations can set policies for the users based on which the DLP system will monitor their activities. Since the information is classified into security classes, documents which are restricted can be detected and remedial actions such as blocks, alerts, and quarantines can be undertaken.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a Data Leak Prevention System is proposed to detect and prevent the data from the leak, thereby achieving the security goals of an organization. The proposed technique has been tested against different scenarios in which the DLP system dealt with various types of data. This technique is simple, easy to implement, and can be useful for many organizations.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Czerwinski, R. Fromm, and T. Hodes, "Digital Music Distribution and Audio Watermarking," <http://www.scientificcommons.org/43025658>, 2007. Available at: www.researchpublications.org NCAICN-2013, PRMITR, Badnera 399
- [2] Y. Li, V. Swarup, and S. Jajodia, "Fingerprinting Relational Databases: Schemes and Specialties," *IEEE Trans. Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 34-45, Jan.-Mar. 2015.
- [3] Y. Cui and J. Widom, "Lineage Tracing for General Data Warehouse Transformations," *The VLDB J.*, vol. 12, pp. 41-58, 2014.
- [4] Panagiotis Papadimitriou and Hector Garcia-Molina, "Data Leakage Detection," *IEEE Trans. Knowledge and Data Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 1, January 2013.
- [5] P. Bonatti, S.D.C. di Vimercati, and P. Samarati, "An Algebra for Composing Access Control Policies," *ACM Trans. Information and System Security*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp.1-35, 2011.

BIOGRAPHIES

Prasad Jadhav is currently pursuing M. Tech from VJTI COE, Mumbai. He has done his B.E.(IT) from Sardar Patel Institute of Technology

Pramila M. Chawan is working as an Associate Professor in the Computer Engineering Department of VJTI, Mumbai. She has done her B. E.(Computer Engg.) and M.E (Computer Engineering) from VJTI COE, Mumbai University. She has 27 years of teaching experience and has guided 75+ M. Tech. projects and 100+ B. Tech. projects. She has published 99 papers in the International Journals, 21 papers in the National/International conferences /symposiums. She has worked as an Organizing Committee member for 13 International Conferences, one National Conference and 4 AICTE workshops. She has worked as NBA coordinator of Computer Engineering Department of VJTI for 5 years. She had written proposal for VJTI under TEQIP-I in June 2004 for creating Central Computing Facility at VJTI. Rs. Eight Crore (Rs. 8,00,00,000/-) were sanctioned by the World Bank on this proposal.